

ENHANCING LISTENING SKILLS IN PSYCHOLOGY STUDENTS THROUGH CLIL METHOD

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Annotation: This article studies the use of the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) method to enhance listening skills in psychology students. It highlights the significance of exposing students to authentic listening materials, including psychology lectures, interviews, podcasts, and therapeutic interactions. By engaging with real-world contexts, accents, and speech patterns, students develop their ability to comprehend and interpret spoken information relevant to their field of study. The article emphasizes the advantages of using authentic materials in CLIL lessons, such as improving listening accuracy, expanding vocabulary, and developing understanding of complex psychological concepts. By incorporating these activities, educators can equip psychology students with the necessary listening skills to develop in their academic and professional development.

Key words: CLIL, enhancing listening skill, contextualized listening

CLIL METODI ORQALI PSIXOLOGIYA YO'NALISHI TALABALARINING INGLIZ TILIDAGI TINGLASH QOBILIYATI RIVOJLANTIRISH

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Kalit so'zlar: CLIL, tinglashni rivojlantirish, kontekstli tinglash

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola psixologiya talabalarida tinglash ko'nikmalarini oshirish uchun CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) usulidan foydalanishni o'rganadi. Bu talabalarni haqiqiy tinglash materiallari, jumladan, psixologiya ma'ruzalari, intervyular, podkastlar va terapevtik o'zaro ta'sirlar bilan tanishtirishning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Real hayotdagi kontekstlar, urg'u va nutq namunalari bilan shug'ullanish orqali talabalar o'zlarining ta'lim sohasiga tegishli og'zaki ma'lumotlarni tushunish va sharhlash qobiliyatini rivojlantiradilar. Maqolada CLIL darslarida tinglash aniqligini oshirish, so'z boyligini kengaytirish va murakkab psixologik tushunchalarni tushunishni kengaytirish kabi autentik materiallardan foydalanishning afzalliklari ta'kidlangan. Ushbu tadbirlarni o'z ichiga olgan holda, o'qituvchilar psixologiya talabalarini o'zlarining akademik va professional rivojlanishlarida ustunlik qilishlari uchun zarur tinglash qobiliyatlarini oshirishlari mumkin.

Introduction: Listening skills play a vital role in the field of psychology, as students need to effectively understand and interpret verbal information from clients, colleagues, and research materials. To develop strong listening skills, the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) method offers a valuable approach. By integrating psychology content into English language lessons, CLIL creates an immersive and contextually meaningful environment for language acquisition, facilitating the development of listening skills alongside subject knowledge. In this article, we will explore the benefits of using the CLIL method to enhance listening skills in psychology students, along with practical strategies and activities.

Benefits of CLIL in Developing Listening Skills:

1. **Authentic Listening Materials:** CLIL exposes students to authentic listening materials, such as psychology lectures, interviews, podcasts, and therapeutic interactions. These materials reflect real contexts, accents, and speech patterns, letting

students to enhance their listening skills by engaging with content relevant to their sphere.

2. **Subject-Specific Vocabulary:** CLIL provides opportunities for students to encounter and practice subject-specific vocabulary and terminology. Listening to psychology-related materials helps students become familiar with discipline-specific language, improving their ability to comprehend and interpret complex information in their future professional settings.

3. **Contextualized Listening:** CLIL integrates listening activities within the broader context of psychology, making the content more meaningful and engaging for students. This contextualization enhances students' motivation to listen attentively and comprehend the information, as it directly relates to their field of study. [Ball Ph.207,p5]:

We try to widen the first among benefits of above:

Engaging students with authentic listening materials is a key aspect of the CLIL method in developing their listening skills. By incorporating psychology lectures, interviews, podcasts, and therapeutic interactions into English language lessons, CLIL exposes students to real-world contexts and provides them with valuable opportunities to practice listening in an authentic and meaningful way.

- Psychology Lectures:** Listening to psychology lectures allows students to familiarize themselves with the academic language, discourse, and concepts used in the field. They can actively listen to professors or experts discussing various topics, theories, and research findings. This exposure helps students grasp complex ideas, expand their vocabulary, and develop the ability to follow extended spoken discourse.

- Interviews:** Listening to interviews with psychologists, researchers, or individuals sharing their personal experiences in the field provides students with valuable insights and perspectives. These interviews often cover diverse topics, such as mental health, human behavior, or therapeutic approaches. Students can improve

their listening skills by understanding different accents, tones, and speech patterns while extracting important information and analyzing the interviewees' viewpoints.

- Podcasts: Incorporating psychology-themed podcasts into CLIL lessons offers an engaging and accessible way for students to improve their listening skills. Podcasts often present discussions, debates, or interviews on psychological topics, delivered in conversational and informal styles. By listening to podcasts, students enhance their ability to comprehend colloquial language, identify main ideas, and follow nuanced discussions.

- Therapeutic Interactions: Listening to recorded therapy sessions or role-plays simulating therapeutic interactions exposes students to real-life scenarios they may encounter in their future careers. Students can observe the dynamics between therapists and clients, identify active listening techniques, and practice understanding clients' concerns, emotions, and perspectives. This helps develop their ability to decipher subtle verbal cues, empathize, and effectively communicate in therapeutic settings.

The inclusion of such authentic listening materials in CLIL lessons not only enhances students' listening comprehension but also provides them with valuable exposure to the language and content they will encounter as psychology professionals. By actively engaging with real-world contexts, accents, and speech patterns, students develop their ability to understand and interpret spoken information, improving their overall listening skills in the field of psychology.

Practical Strategies and Activities:

1. Authentic Listening Tasks: Select authentic listening materials, such as psychology lectures, TED Talks, or interviews with psychologists, and create comprehension tasks. Ask students to listen for specific information, identify main ideas, or summarize key points. Encourage active listening strategies, such as note-taking and predicting content, to enhance comprehension skills.

2. Group Discussions: After listening to a psychology-related audio clip, facilitate group discussions where students can share their interpretations, opinions,

and reflections. Encourage active participation, critical thinking, and the use of newly acquired vocabulary in the discussions. This activity improves not only listening skills but also speaking and critical analysis skills.

3. **Case Study Analysis:** Present audio recordings of therapy sessions or psychological case studies for students to analyze. Ask students to listen attentively and extract related information, such as client background, presenting issues, or therapeutic interventions. Afterward, engage students in a discussion about the case, encouraging them to apply their listening comprehension skills to analyze and discuss the content.

4. **Note-taking Practice:** Provide students with opportunities to practice effective note-taking skills during listening activities. Encourage them to develop shorthand techniques, focus on capturing key points, and organize their notes for future reference. This activity helps students improve their listening accuracy, retention, and ability to extract essential information.

5. **Listening to Academic Talks:** Select psychology-related academic talks, research presentations, or conferences, and assign students to listen to these recordings. Provide comprehension questions or discussion prompts related to the content of the talk. This activity exposes students to academic discourse in psychology, improving their listening skills in academic settings. [Meyer O.2000,p 6]

Conclusion: Incorporating the CLIL method in teaching English to psychology students offers significant benefits for the development of listening skills. By integrating psychology content into language lessons, students engage with authentic listening materials, practice subject-specific vocabulary, and experience contextualized listening experiences. Through activities such as authentic listening tasks, group discussions, case study analysis, note-taking practice, and exposure to academic talks, students can enhance their listening comprehension, critical thinking, and understanding of psychology concepts. By utilizing the CLIL approach, educators can equip psychology students with the necessary listening skills to excel in their academic

pursuits and professional careers, enabling effective communication and comprehension in the field of psychology.

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